
RETOOLING TEACHERS FOR IMPROVED STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS IN PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN PORT HARCOURT CITY LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

By

Dr. Chijioke Clancy Amadi

Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education.

Email: chijiokeclancy@gmail.com

Tel: [08035406780](tel:08035406780)

Dr. Bema Barida Nubari

Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education.

Email: bema.barida@gmail.com

Tel: [08063518499](tel:08063518499)

Abstract

The study investigated retooling teachers for improved students' academic achievements in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. The purpose of the study was to examine the ways retooling teachers' can improve student academic achievements for enhanced school management service delivery. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population comprised 700 teachers in 16 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. The sample size was 350 teachers using the simple random sampling technique which represented 50% of the population. A validated instrument titled "retooling teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools questionnaire (RTISAAPSSSQ)" was used for data collection. The reliability coefficient gave 0.88 for the study, and a modified Likert's four-point scale was used. Mean, SD and rank order statistics were used to answer research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion mean of 2.50 was accepted and below 2.50 was rejected. The result revealed that teachers agreed that in-service training, collaborative technology amongst others facilitates timeless creativity with the fast-paced nature of education and net generation of learners. It was concluded that qualitative academic delivery rests upon the teacher embracing 21st century academic skills. It was recommended that teachers should be given their appraisal score sheets carried out by the principals and the Ministry of Education in order to enhance their mastery and experience in teaching profession. Teachers should not be stereotyped to one professional development programme but should be allowed to frequently participate in all-round development.

Keywords: Retooling, Teachers, Students Academic Achievements, Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Introduction

In a contemporary school system, the attainment of qualitative education delivery is dependent on the efficiency of teachers in the system, this can be achieved if teachers broaden their knowledge for competitive advantage. We live in a transformational driven age where the goal is to create a new stream of ideas, creativity and deepen learning which promotes career development and advancement for organizational well being. However, this objective cannot be achieved if teachers are not competent enough to impart the required knowledge and skills to succeed in life. This is because the role of a teacher is enormous and central in the development of a nation. As society changes, so does its demand and expectations of the school change. The schools cannot remain static, otherwise it will produce learners that cannot make any meaningful impact on the society. Retooling teachers is an important investment in the future of the students. This helps to ensure that students have opportunity to achieve their academic potentials.

The term retooling in education is a process of rearranging components of an existing course to align better with personalized learning needs of 21st century learner. Retooling is developing or building up whatever skills one already has to equip him or her better in performance of his/her statutory job function. The need for retooling is to reflect current and emerging technology trend in teachers' instructional delivery outcome. Retooling can transform and revolutionized teaching, independent learning, assessment and other educational initiatives, comprehensive understanding of technology aids qualitative research and quality instructional delivery for competitive advantage. Retooling imbued with technology has been viewed as a method rather than a tool to facilitate and support teaching and not the other way around and it is sometimes believed that if computers are placed in the hand of teacher, these devices will transform teaching and learning processes.

Objectively, as school curriculum changes with society, teachers will need some continuous development so that they can grow in competence and handle changes that come with social, political, technological, economic and ideological change in the society. These expectations have broadened the tasks of teachers, particularly in areas of teaching largely heterogeneous students who came from different background and culture.

Apart from teachers inculcating skills to students, contemporary teachers are required to be technologically compliant in teaching and learning process, students' assessment, record keeping and other documentations. However, Ikegusi and Modebelu (2016) observed that knowledge of how to use computer and its peripheries has in recent times become essentials tools in performance of education tasks. This implies that modern teachers are also expected to be competent in imparting higher order thinking skills in students, particularly decisive skills such as analytical thinking, creative thinking, problem solving among others.

These suggest that in this new generation of learners (digital native) and rapidly changing world teachers need to increase their competencies, knowledge-base, teaching skills and teaching technique through trainings and personal development effort with a view to acquiring new knowledge and methods to leverage on innovations and new technologies designed to improve instructional delivery experiences and students' learning outcomes. Buttressing this point, Obaya (2014) in Ukaigwe and Adieme (2018:32) asserted that there is need to train teachers to improve their knowledge and professional effectiveness in order to replace dated pedagogical practices that underpin the educational system in Nigeria Secondary Schools.

In the same vein, Ukaigwe and Onwumere (2018) maintained that involvement of teachers in capacity-building programmes is one of the key ways of equipping them with essential teaching skills that aid maximal productivity and enhanced academic performance of students. This implies that the degree of knowledge acquired by the teacher determines the level of competence. Teachers' quality helps to promote knowledge which creates sustainable future for the youths and as well equips student with skills for sustainable development.

To this end, it is pertinent to note that teachers' development is a prerequisite for national development since the economy of any nation and its rate of growth depends on adequate trained/skilled workers (teachers).

Students' academic achievement is foundational goal to education, as it portrays the level to which students have acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for lifelong success. Academic achievement of students is not just passing examinations; it is essential to their self- advancement, employment prospects, and contribution to the society. Teachers, at which the implantation of curriculum lies must equip themselves with knowledge, skills, and current teaching techniques to meet students' demands, bridge learning gaps, and inspire learners to reach their full potential. This is because teachers are at the heart of students learning and their preparedness directly influenced learners' performance. In the words of Fullan (2007) noted that without committed and competent teachers, curriculum reforms remain unfulfilled, as teachers act as change agents in the learning process. Similarly, Ornstein and Hunkins (2018) asserted that effective curriculum practice requires teachers to adapt instruction to students' needs, integrate assessment, and create inclusive classrooms. To remain relevant in this information age, the teachers must continually upgrade their knowledge and skills in various areas of their profession, so that they can be able to perform their statutory task adequately. However, this study shall be reviewed under the following headings: collaboration technology skill, in-service training and staff appraisal. This is the subject matter.

Concept Definition

In this era, nothing happens through sheer chance there must be rational decisions and objectives to be pursued. The need for teachers to be prepared to teach in this fast changing world and net generation of learner is fast demanding. Definition of retooling of teachers may vary depending on the context and individual scholar's perspective.

Conceptualizing retooling of teachers, Fullan and Hargreaves (2014) sees it as the process of preparing them to teach in a changing world they emphasized that the need for teachers to be prepared to teach in a world that is constantly changing is fast demanding. It suggests that retooling teachers is essential for ensuring that students are prepared for the future. Gukskey, (2007), retooling teaching is the process of providing them with professional development they need to improve their teaching practices and students learning. They emphasizes the importance of professional development is helping teachers improve their teaching practice and student learning. He stressed further that retooling teachers is an ongoing process that should be tailored to the individual's needs of teacher.

However, these definitions emphasize the importance of helping teachers develop new skills and attitude in order to meet the changing needs of students and society. This is because, at the implementation of curriculum lies the teachers, in other word, Mishra, et al (2009), defined retooling teachers as the process of equipping them with new skills and knowledge needed to teach in a new ways, using new technologies, and addressing the needs of a diverse students population. This implies that the need for teachers to develop new skills and

knowledge is imperative, in order to use technology effectively in classroom to address the needs of students for competitive advantage.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework below shows a diagrammatic representation of retooling teachers for improved student's academic achievements.

Statement of the Problem

There is no gainsaying whatsoever that every sustainable economy strives with education and teachers' quality is a yardstick and veritable factor to be reckoned with as far as his job effectiveness is concerned. Therefore, their competence determines to a great extent the quality of teaching and learning outcome. Preliminary observation of the research suggests that many teachers exhibit low performance in various areas of their job in secondary schools in Rivers State. This could be the fact that they lack some teaching skills which depicts non-realization of quality education delivery in schools. The consequences of these may likely reflect on student low performance in school. In view of the above problems, the researcher considers it imperative to carry out this study to examine whether retooling teachers such as: collaboration technology, in-service training, staff appraisal among others can enhance teachers' job for improved students academic achievements.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine retooling tool of teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Areas of Rivers State. Specifically, the objective of the study sought;

1. Investigate the various retooling tool of teachers for improved students' academic achievements in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State
2. Identify the extent in-service training can enhance teachers for improved students academic achievements in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area.
3. Examine the extent collaboration technology can enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government in Rivers State.
4. Find out how staff appraisal can enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the various retooling tool of teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?
2. What extent does in-service training enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt city of Rivers State?
3. To what extent the collaboration technology enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievements in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area in Rivers State?
4. In what way does staff appraisal enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers' response on the various retooling tool of teachers for improved students academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers' response on the extent in-service training enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

HO₃: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers' response on the extent collaboration technology enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

HO₄: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers' response on the how staff appraisal/feedback can enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government in Rivers State.

Theoretical Framework

The pedagogical content knowledge theory was used to guide this study, and it was propounded by Lee Shulman in 1986. While examining the dichotomous knowledge of teacher's education, which are pedagogical skills and content knowledge of specialty. He opposed the polarization of teachers' preparation process into content knowledge and pedagogy, arguing that the two domains should be combined to ensure harmony of purpose and effectiveness in preparation of teachers. The scholar put forward the concept of Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) as a model in teachers capacity building exercise.. Shulman, remarked that knowledge's is all about how teaching and learning proceeds through contextualized and guided process the teacher observes in classroom to effect learning in students. Whereas the pedagogical content entails good knowledge of subject – specialty the practical knowledge of how to structure learning contents and experiences in orderly and sequential manner to smother teaching, on the part teachers and comprehension on the part of students the implication of this theory is that teachers professional development should be driven objective geared towards knowledge of content in disciplinary specialty and acquisition of pedagogical skills that will facilitate knowledge transfer.

Teacher

An effective teacher is one who is proficient in knowledge and has ability to inculcate skills and knowledge to the learner in order to bring about change in behavior of learner. This change in behavior of learner is based on predetermined educational objectives and is an indication that learning has taken place and that the teacher has taught. Teachers effectiveness is the knowledge, strategies, process which leads to good learning outcome. An effective teacher is proactive and has a positive impact on their student and expertise to improve instructional delivery. These good outcomes are often those that can be measured easily, usually through summative assessment. The goal of education is to produce reflective and reasonable learners and this can occur through the teaching of thinking skills. The teacher as an indispensable resource in the educational organization teaching and learning depend on him because he/she is charged with the responsibility of converting raw materials (learners) into furnished products educated, disciplined, employable and productive thinking individuals. As the key agent in curriculum implementation, it is on the teacher that the success and failure of any curriculum depends. This obligation is no doubt very challenging and crucial and therein lies the effectiveness of teachers.

However, Adams as cited in Achumonye (2008) posited that a teacher affects eternity. He can never tell where his influence stop. This implies that the teacher has always been the mainstays of intellectual progress of any society, and the corner stone of personal happiness of every student. This implies that the teacher gives the learner, some of his cherished wisdom, usually made up abundance of facts and other supposedly true information. Agi (2010) posited that teacher effectiveness are critical instrument in the transmission of knowledge and worthwhile values. In the same vein, Essien (1997) as cited in Achuonye (2008) stated that an education that enhance national development depends largely on the teachers as no matter how well equipped the institution may be not much will be achieved in terms of manpower training in absence of trained and well motivated teachers. As the society changes, so does the people demand and expect school to change via competent teachers.

Consequently, teachers-effectiveness centered primarily on helping learner to learn and the teacher does not only bring about learning but accept responsibility failing to do so. The teacher whose learners fail to understand his subject has at least some explanation to give for

his inability to deliver. The learner may lack motivation, but it is the duty of the teacher to provide the necessary motivation in the classroom through his wealth of experience.

Collaboration Technology

Collaboration technology is a promising method of human commitment that has become a twenty-first-century pattern. The need to brainstorm together and cooperate on basic issues has become an essential means of teachers' job effectiveness. However, Johnson, Johnson and Smilt (2007) stated that collaborative oriented learning can advance academic and social educational outcome.

Collaboration technology is a contemporary tool in a modern day qualitative educational delivery which enhances and encourages an open system of ideology, team work and administrative progress, in accordance with the system theory, Open system operation are continuity of positive vision of education in Nigeria, which collaboration technology is a secret ingredient for all round success in the enhancement of academic performance of students. It stands as a vital tool, indispensable idea which when effectively and efficiently utilized will undoubtedly enhance students' performance level for competitive advantage. Jacqueline et al (2006) describe collaboration as an educational device that can be used to meet the needs of diverse students and fulfill their expected goals which gears towards enhancing the students performance. Collaboration technology models are transforming the way educators teach and students engagement in classroom instructional delivery. Collaboration technology in recent time helps expand access to education with it schools have the ability to reach out to more students. Using video, and online introduction can be effective as traditional face-to-face interaction. Collaboration technology is a solutions to help keep schools at the forefront of education both technically and academically. Collaborative technology skills is internet driven, and it is a compulsory skill needed of teachers to promote 21st century workforce, especially in this net generation of learners. Collaboration technology skill acquire is a viable tool for learning. Imagine a teacher without internet driven skills in this information age, this might lead to unhealthy phenomenon to the educational system, specifically to the teachers at which the implementation of curriculum lies.

The sudden outbreak of covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria led to closure of schools, hospital, market business centres among others became an eye opener for Nigerians that the needs to cultivate and embrace the culture of digital technology classroom or essential during this pandemic. But in the first world countries collaboration technology keeps them in class. Collaboration technology deepens learning which helps promote problem solving abilities, critical thinking, innovative ideas among others for overall students learning outcome. Its basis is to connect learners from different background together at the same time to brainstorm which harness and inspire creativity for a long useful life. It is believed that when educators brainstorm together from cross cultural background, they strengthen their weakness, develop skills which promote career development and advancement. The essence is to increase efficiency and productiveness among educators for healthy school climate.

However, collaboration technology in education can facilitate students' academic achievement in the following ways:

Boost learners success: Empowers learners to achieve a desires result regardless of device or location.

Personalize learning: Aroused learners to gain knowledge or skill at their own pace via combined flipped learning.

Raised learners engagement: Furnish learners with technology tools to access content and collaborate with contemporary and educators.

Students' performance when enhanced stands a positive door of opportunity for the growth of the school and these goes a long way into advertising the school before the public and increasing the academic, economic and financial status quo of any secondary school. Students' performance will only increase greatly and be enhanced when collaboration technology is in place.

In-Service Training

In-service training is a type of professional development that is provided to teachers while they are already employed. It is a valuable tool for retooling teachers and improving skills.

There is a consensus in literature that the building up and efficiency of an organization whether private or public depends to a large extent how effectively the workforce (teachers) are well equipped for an organization to attain its desired objectives in this 21st century workforce for competitive advantage. However, any organization that lay little or no emphasis on training and development is encouraging the obsolescence of employees, encouraging inflexibility in the organization. Ebong (2006) sees training as a short term educational programme that are made available to employees to enable them acquire technical skills and knowledge relevant for a particular job. Hooker (2009) asserted that teachers development is a systematized initial and continuous coherent and modular process of professional development of educators in a conformity with professional competency standard and framework. In the same vein Amien (2013) asserted that training is a systematic way of acquiring new knowledge on how an employee should do his/her job creditably. In other words, development aims at providing employee skills and competences for anticipated future job performance (Sims, 2002). Nevertheless, Nwabueze (2011) outlined the benefit of training and development in employee to include:

- i. Career advancement
- ii. Increased Productivity
- iii. High moral standard
- iv. Improve on existing Skills.

The above clarifies the needs for teachers' development for teachers' standard and produce changes in instructional teachers practices and also serve as a motivating factor for job effectiveness as well as for the acquisitions of skills and knowledge that prepares them for greater responsibilities. In a related development Quink (2011) asserted that teachers' development programme is a formal in-service training to improve the content knowledge and pedagogical skills of teachers, that is widely viewed as important means of improving teaching and learning for optimum productivity. Stressing on this Ezekiel-Hart (2007) noted that teaching is a demanding job that required in-depth knowledge of subject matter, content, handling of instructional material and the use of may varied skills and attitudes. The quality of training a teacher does a long way towards isolating effective teachers from ineffective ones.

This implies that the level of which knowledge can be achieved depends to a large extent on the quality of training received by the teachers. The idea is to inspire and harness creativity for a long useful. It is believed developing teacher professionally, economically, scientifically, and knowledge-wise will automatically place them in a better position transform the students for a long useful living in the society. It is normal for teachers to pursue vigorously and acquire pedagogical skills required for effective teaching and learning

process in the school. This is because education for sustainable development is recognized to be very important and central to the success of sustainable development all over the world.

According to Okeke (2004):

Teacher education and training are designed to equip the teacher to immediate needs as well as long term professional needs. The programmes are well intended to properly equip the teacher as agents for the dissemination of certain kinds of socially approved knowledge, skills and attitudes to rising generation; innovations in the modernization process and agent of community uplift. In essence, the teacher education should be viewed as lifeline development plan for the teacher (p.96). This implies that teachers' knowledge factor is critical to educational well being. Nation that succeeded in education and development takes teachers seriously.

The school were primarily established to educate it's citizenry via, a competent teachers. To accomplished these laudable objectives, organization needs well trained, and devoted teachers to implement the curriculum, in line with global best practices. It is pertinent to note that developing teachers conceptual skills, attitudes, knowledge will enhance their performance. Teachers are the most indispensable component of any education system, because they transform the behaviour, attitude and thinking of the learners in real teaching/learning classroom operation. This proposition is buttressed by Abraham (2003) who sees the school as a means of transmitting the acceptable values and norms of society to pupils and students. It therefore, has the responsibility of ensuring that it's product are found worthy both in character and in learning: that can compete favourably with peers anywhere in the world.

The effectiveness of any education is determine mainly by the caliber of teachers, thus, training and continuous development of teachers is a necessity for a competitive advantage. There is a paradigm shift today in knowledge most competitive system as knowledge is being revolutionized, critiqued and reformed on daily basis. This dynamism has made it mandatory for teacher's to embark on in-service training to be accommodated in our technologically changing society. This proposition is buttressed by, Edem (2014) who posits that school administrator has a challenging task in providing adequate in-service programmes aimed at improving both the collective performance of his staff and the in-service programme is a mechanism design to facilitate and broaden mental capabilities of teachers, for technological advancement. Job training has a vital force on teachers performance because, its' geared towards moulding and modifying their skills, attitude and knowledge. Job training regenerate mind, and established sound relationship between teacher and his job.

In-service training as been conceptualize by different scholars. Eghonmwan (2018) sees in-services education programems as a programme aimed towards updating and developing employees knowledge and skills by reorientation and modeling their attitudes, so that they can be more proficient in performance of their job. The scholar further said that, this development becomes Imperative because no employees has accomplished the level of perfection at the time of hiring. They need to update, upgrade and develop their knowledge, from the day they are hired, till the day they retired. To Musset (2010), in-service education programme is a training geared at developing, and boarding teachers' knowledge directed by the school, that contribute to the occupational competence and growth of the employee. For Iwundu (2008), in-service education is education received in a structural setting that enables one to become more competent professionally, to further develop technical subject matter competences in order to keep abreast of and if possible ahead of change, to explore educational and technological content and processes in varying depths and to increase

personal competences. This enables them to improve their professional knowledge, skills and attitudes in order that they can educate learners more effectively.

Apparently, an organization that puts great emphasis on in-service training for the employee is directly planning for its survival. To performance optimally, it is important and beneficial for teachers to go through continuous and regular training to learn new things on how to perform their task better. Teachers who remain up-to-date on new research can how to help children to learn, new tools and skills and emerging technology and so on through continuous in-service programmes. This proposition enjoys scholarly support by Ozor and Onuoha (2015) who sees in-service training as a form of training offered by the employers to the employees to develop their skills to enable them perform effectively and efficiently. This approach enable them acquire and applied modern skills, in line with global best practices.

Basically, educating teachers through in-services is one of the best ways of projecting them towards excellence in job performance. For instance Walton (2005) conducted a study on influence of workshop /conference on job performance of teacher: The study revealed a significant influence of workshops/conference on teachers' outputs: the scholars reveal that teachers should be regularly provided with chances to attend/workshops/conferences, in order to acquire skills for high productivity in school. However, Ekpele (2005) has identified the root cause of teachers low productivity outputs. These include; unpreparedness in terms of skills update, lack exposure to work shops/conference. The scholar maintained that employees should be inspired to embrace training to improve quality outputs. Thus creating chances and cultivating the culture of sustainable development programmes for teachers, will improve quality teaching and learning for a competitive advantage.

Obviously, employees training when on their job remain a vital force in efficient administration. The assumption is that in-service training enlighten employees realize better way they can to do their work, develop their skills for effective job performance. This proficiency can be fostered through in-service training. In-services education encompasses all activities engaged in professional personnel services during their services and is aimed to contribute professional improvement on the job. Developing employees frequently has a major effect or notable control on the level of output, and the result that an institution observed. However, as employees increases in skills they are more fit to carried out more tasks and execute their functions effectively. Employee training is not something that is done once to employees it is used continuously in every reputable institution. As technology changes, so it requires updating the skills and knowledge of teachers in their profession.

Based on these propositions, Roa (1996) outlined the benefits of employees' training when on their job. These include:

- i. To develop the potentialities of workers
- ii. To prepare employees meet the present as well as the changing requirement of the job and the organization.
- iii. To prepare employee functions effectively in their respective position
- iv. To prevent obsolescence
- v. To assist employees to function more higher level task and
- vi. To promote individual and collective morale, a sense of responsibility, co-operative attitudes and good relationship.

The effects of these measure makes employee performs creditably. Consequently, the teachers need in-service programmes on the job so as to perform effectively in ever changing work environment. Competent employee do not remain the same forever, skills deteriorate

and can be obsolete, that is why organization spend money on re-training of their workforce. In-service education is considered to be an important measure of teachers' competence and this explains why most organization organizes in-services training programmes for re-training of teachers from time to time to provide professional growth.

However, it has been established by Nnabuo (1996) that teachers cannot be expected to give what they do not possess. Staff development programmes help teachers to be current while improving themselves to effect quality education in their various schools. He further found out that low achieving learners increased their achievement levels by as much as 53% effect when they are taught by a highly effective teachers. The ultimate goal of staff development programme is either to improve an observed deficiency in some area of education or to increase efficiency or to bring to focus the implementations of educational innovations, this he said.

The above overview suggests that in-service remains one of the ways to sustain teachers to adapt to the changing situation in this technological world. This is so because teaching has become a way to stay innovative and grow faster.

Staff Appraisal

Staff appraisal is a process of evaluating the performance level of employee. It is an imparted tool for providing feedback, identify areas for improvement and develop employee skills. Teachers who receive regular feedback on their teaching will likely to improve their instruction and see gains in their student's achievement. Feedback can help teachers identify areas where they can improve, and it can also motivate them to continue learning and growing.

The cardinal focus of staff appraisal is to improve teaching and learning process, and evaluate employee performance. Staff appraisal is a comprehensive and supportive developmental process. It is designed to help teachers to acquire the pre-requisite skills, and support they require to carry out their function effectively. It assists on making sure that teachers are able to continue to enhance their professional practice and develop as a teacher. There is no doubt whatsoever that teachers' professional competence is crucial for the survival of the school system and also important for quality education delivery. The staff appraisal system helps in recognizing and encouraging correct performance, determining areas for development and enhances overall teacher's performance. The need for performance is well accepted in all successful organization all over the world. Its purpose is to find out how effectively an employee has done the job for which he was hired.

Obviously, appraisal is not only design to nurture teachers' development but also to identify opportunities for further supports on the part of teacher. Staff appraisal helps to regenerate employee (teacher) in their workplace, which helps employee to work and create an atmosphere where there is more acceptance of ideas and changes in organization (school system) for effective functioning of the school. A successful organization is one in which all members working towards the attainment of the same goal. Every member contributes something different, but all works towards the same direction which is improving, school organization. It is therefore necessary for an organization (school system) to conduct regular appraisal, in order to provide corresponding programmes to ensure performance.

Appraisal is geared towards assisting a teacher to become as effective as possible in teaching and learning process and also towards meeting, a teacher's needs through professional development programmes: for example in-service training. Appraisal should not be view as a

mechanism for fault-finding and criticizing, but as a means of building the teachers positive self-image and motivation to be as good a teacher as possible.

Conceptualizing staff appraisal, Nwobueze (2011) asserts that staff appraisal is a systematic process use to ascertain the entire worth of academic staff to school system because it analyses the success of teachers' failure and entire work performance in the system. To Decenzo and Robins (2005), staff appraisal is a mechanism design in the evaluating, analyzing an employee assign task with major aim of appreciating, rewarding, revising employee performance. In the word of Taylor (2003), staff appraisal provide the opportunity for employees to received structured, constructive advices and framed feedback about their job and growth and capability.

In the light of the foregoing analyses, it has been established that staff appraisal helps in conveying meaningful feedback for maintaining a capable workforce in an organization (school system) for productivity. More importantly, the importance of appraisal to employee (teachers) can hardly be over-emphasized. This because it gives feedback on how well the staff is doing and how the organization (school system perceives their contributions to the entire organization effort). In any organization, employers constantly evaluate the performance of the employee. This process helps in ensuring that the employees (teachers) do their job creditably for a competitive advantage. An appraisal exercise is very crucial to organization well being, because a superior is passing judgment on the performance of a subordinate. The employee knows that management (school system) is going to determine his future prospect from his present and past performance, why he wait anxiously to know whether they see it as he does. An appraisal is a supportive measure used to inform employee about continuing professional development. This proposition enjoys scholarly support of Berman (2005) who asserts that appraisal and advancement is a turning point in developing and maintaining a strong competent manpower. He asserts further that through staff appraisal an organization will be able to discover whether there are re-training needs for teachers. Appraisal is integral part of professional development of teachers. It is quite different from supervisory function of school administrator it is view as a professional partnership in which the person leading the appraisal will seek out the abilities of those been appraisal rather than searching for incompetence's. However, Arikewuyo and Adegbesan averse that staff appraisal assists to: Identify both individuals and group weakness and strength so that weakness can be corrected and strengths develop upon: Identify the hopes and aspiration of individuals where are not in conflict with the organization's objective.

Nevertheless, a poor appraisal system could create ill feelings resulting in low morale that could be costly to the organization. That is why those appraising need to update their knowledge in order to carry out their task effectively. It is pertinent to note that one of the important functions of educational manager is the performance appraisal of the teachers. It is almost the accepted norm that the educational manager is the best qualified to evaluate his performance and make informed judgement about his personal and potential qualities. The educational manager is accountable to management for the performance of the teachers. Common sense dictates that he must be knowledgeable and responsible for making decisions that will affect their behaviour.

However, Cole (2002) contends that conducting frequent stall appraisal is crucial workforce development strategy for organization such as schools. He further asserts that staff appraisal offer a valuable opportunity to recognize staff efforts and performance, discover key obstacles and facilitation work practices and identify professional development needs for

employees. Indeed school system requires regular appraisal because organization performance depends on quality level of their employees.

Consequently, Nwachukwu (1988) outline key factors to be considered in all performance evaluation;

- i. Be objective and consistent in evaluating employees. Always ask yourself, am I being fair”.
- ii. Never base performance appraisal on personal characteristic only.
- iii. Performance appraisal must be complete. It must review the past and the present, and potential for the future.
- iv. Be ready at all times to justify claims or assertions about an employee’s performance.
- v. The outcome of the evaluation should not be a total surprise to employees. Give feedbacks.
- vi. Every appraisal must be followed by an interview to discuss the rating and ways of improving performance.
- vii. Neither employee performance evaluation, nor the interview, should be done in a hurry.
- viii. Help the employee to set his own goals and work out with him the systematic steps to be taken for its accomplishment.

Employees reaction to performance appraisal is very significant factor since it could affect job performance, hence appraisal is designed to improve results. The importance of this exercise which affects productivity and job satisfaction should be well understood by employees. A concerted effort should be made to “sell” the importance of the exercise to employees (teachers) who are expected to benefit from it. It is imperative also that educational managers who perform the appraisal should be well trained, if appraisal exercise is to be meaningful. This approach clarifies the fact that acquiring more knowledge has become a way to stay innovative, grow faster in this technological world, in line with global best practices.

Methodology

The design for the study was descriptive survey design. The population comprised seven hundred (700) teachers 185 male and 515 female in 16 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government areas of Rivers State (Sources: Planning, research and statistics department, RSSSB, Port Harcourt, Rivers State). A sample size of the study was 350 teachers. The stratified random sampling gave 350 teachers which represented 50% of the population. Retooling teachers for improve students’ academic achievement (RTISAAPSSSQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was a self-designed structured question on a four point modified likert scale of very high-extent (VHE) 4, High Extent (HE) 3, Low Extent (LE) 2, Very Low Extent (VLE) 1. The instrument was made up of two sections. Section A was used to collect information on demographic variables of the respondents while section B comprised 15 items designed to obtain answers to research questions for the study. Face and content validity was done by three experts in measurement and evaluation for content modification and corrections. The internal consistency reliability method was determined through Cronbach alpha reliability statistics which gave reliability index of 0.88. Mean and rank order statistics were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the various retooling tool of teachers for improved students academic achievements in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government of Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on the retooling tool of teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government of Rivers State

S/N	The various retooling tool of teachers for improved students academic achievements	Mean	Std	Decision
1	Collaboration technology	3.43	.39	Agreed
2.	In-service Training	3.28	.40	Agreed
3.	Communication Skills	3.13	.41	Agreed
4.	Content knowledge	3.11	.49	Agreed
5.	Staff Appraisal	2.90	.45	Agreed
Aggregate mean		3.37		Agreed

Data on table 1 revealed that items with serial numbers 1 to 5 have their various mean values above the criterion mean of 2.50 and were agreed by the respondents as the various retooling tool of teachers for improved students academic achievements in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government of Rivers State. The various retooling tool of teachers for improved students academic achievements are: collaboration technology, in-service training, communication skills, content knowledge, and staff appraisal

Research Question 2: What are the ways collaboration technology enhance teachers' job for improved students academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt city local government area of Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on the areas collaboration technology improves students academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt city local government area of Rivers State

S/N	Ways collaboration technology enhance teachers' job for improved student academic achievement	Mean	Std	Decision
6.	Active listening	2.80	.45	Agreed
7.	Inclusivity skills	3.19	.40	Agreed
8.	Critical thinking	2.78	.49	Agreed
9.	Creative innovation	3.30	.42	Agreed
10.	Communication	3.20	.48	Agreed
Aggregate mean		3.05		Agreed

Data on table 2 revealed that items with serial numbers have their various mean above the criterion mean of 2.50 and were agreed by the teachers as the ways collaboration technology enhances teachers' job for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt city local government area of Rivers State. The ways collaboration technology enhance teachers' job for improved students academic achievement are through active listening, inclusivity skills, critical thinking, creative innovation and communication.

Research Question 3: To what extent does in-service training enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area of Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation on the extent in-service training can enhance teachers for improved students' academic achievements in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area of Rivers State.

S/N	The extent in-service training enhances teachers for improved students academic achievement	Mean	Std	Decision
11.	Pedagogical skill	3.57	.49	VHE
12.	Productivity	2.68	.45	HE
13.	Innovative nature	3.00	.42	HE
14.	Broadens mental capabilities	2.58	.50	HE
15.	Increases effectiveness	2.73	.49	HE
Aggregate mean		2.91		HE

Data on table 3 revealed that the aggregate mean value is 2.91 and falls within the categorization of High Extent. Therefore, in-service training enhances teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area of Rivers State to a high extent.

Research Question 4: To what extent does staff appraisal enhances teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area of Rivers State?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation on the extent staff appraisal enhances teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area of Rivers State.

S/N	The extent staff appraisal enhances teachers for improved student academic achievement	Mean	Std	Decision
16.	Provide information on learning need	3.43	.49	VHE
17.	Enhances performance level	3.14	.35	HE
18.	Motivate for continuous learning and growing	3.40	.46	VHE
19.	Identifies opportunities for areas of support	3.00	.49	HE
20.	Help to regenerate areas of weakness	3.57	.49	VHE
Aggregate mean		2.91		VHE

Data on table 4 revealed that the aggregate mean value is 3.31 and falls within the categorization of Very High Extent. Therefore, staff appraisal enhances teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area of Rivers State to a very high extent.

Summary of Findings

The findings of this study are summarized as shown below:

1. The various retooling tool of teachers for improved students' academic achievements are: collaboration technology, in-service training, communication skills, content knowledge, and staff appraisal.
2. The various ways collaboration technology can enhance teachers' job for improved students' academic achievement are through active listening, inclusivity skills, critical thinking, creative innovation and communication.
3. It was found that in-service training enhances teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area of Rivers State to a high extent.
4. It was revealed that staff appraisal enhances teachers for improved students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt City local government area of Rivers State to a very high extent.

Conclusion

Education through teaching is a profound activity done by the teacher in a professional way. Therefore teachers' knowledge level remains a determinant factor for accomplishment of educational objectives, as an essential ingredient for positive impact. Hence, to achieve this laudable objective, the teachers must embrace 21st century workforce skill for efficient and effective functioning of educational system in line with global best practices.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should be given appraisal score sheets carried out by the principals and the ministry of education in order to enhanced their mastery and experience in teaching profession.
2. Teachers should not be stereotyped to one professional development programmes, but should be allowed to frequently participate in all round development.
3. Promotion of teachers should be tied on numbers of workshops, conference, attended this will.
4. There should be timely training of teachers on ICT related areas

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